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CORRESPONDING OF CURRENT ASSETS ACCOUNTING TO INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the views of foreign and domestic scholars on current assets, as well as economic resources and requirements, and the concept and composition of current assets in their composition. A definition for assets and current assets has been developed. A proposal on the composition of current assets in accordance with international standards has been developed. Special directions for improving the current assets of the current balance sheet are proposed.

Keywords: economic resources and claims, current assets, financial reporting, non-current assets, accounts receivable.

INTRODUCTION

On February 24, 2020, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4611 “On additional measures for the transition to international financial reporting standards” [1] was adopted. In accordance with this resolution, from January 1, 2021, joint-stock companies, commercial banks, and enterprises belonging to the category of large taxpayers are required to submit their reports in accordance with international financial reporting standards (IFRS). In solving these important tasks, the study of international standards and foreign experience is of great importance. To do this, it is necessary to carefully study each term in IFRS, analyze it and apply a methodology for its implementation. International standards define assets as economic resources that generate economic benefit. Therefore, the study of assets, including current assets, which are its component, is an urgent issue. The research substantiated the need to bring asset accounting, including current assets accounting, into line with international standards. The composition of assets in the current balance sheet does not meet the requirements of international standards. Today, there is a need to create a modern balance sheet format. Based on the above, it can be noted that

improving the accounting of current assets in accordance with international standards is a pressing issue.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Economic resources in the economic sense are the set of all tangible and intangible resources used in the financial and economic activities of a company. They include natural resources (natural resources, including land, subsoil, biological assets), capital (money and means of production), labor resources (work and employees), and intangible resources (intellectual property and entrepreneurial talent).

The new conceptual framework for financial reporting [2] introduced the concept of “economic resources and requirements”. According to it, financial statements for general use should provide information about the financial position of the reporting entity. Information about the financial position mainly includes information about the economic resources of the entity and the requirements for them. Financial statements also provide information about the effects of transactions and other events that lead to changes in the economic resources of the organization and the requirements for them, which information serves as a basis for making decisions about the allocation of resources to the organization’s management.

Saud J. Mashkour Alamru stated that “Current assets represent the value of all assets that are expected to be converted into cash within one year in the normal course of business. Current assets include inventories, accounts receivable, marketable securities, cash, prepaid expenses, and other liquid assets that can be easily converted into cash” [5].

In his scientific research, U.A. Nurmanov stated that "Current assets are mobile assets of an economic entity in constant motion, assets that fully transfer their value and form to the products being created during one production (normative operating) cycle, and they include inventories, expenses of the future period, deferred expenses, cash, short-term investments, debtors and other current assets" [10] described as.

The following formula for current assets is widely used in the literature:

“Current assets = Cash + Cash Equivalents + Inventory + Accounts Receivable + Market Securities + Prepaid Expenses + Other Liquid Assets” [7]

In the context of the global economy’s transition to a digital economy, the concept of “digital assets” is emerging in accounting. American scholar Neil Amato, in his article in the most prestigious US journal “Accountancy” [6], notes that digital assets are being introduced by professional organizations, and shows the methodology for their calculation and audit.

The definition of the concept of “current assets” in the literature in our country does not meet the requirements of international standards. There is a need to bring the composition of current assets into line with the requirements of international standards

in regulatory and legal documents and approved forms of financial reporting. In practice, accountants feel the lack of methodological recommendations that are consistent with the requirements of the standards in assessing, recording and reflecting current assets in reports.

IAS 1 [3] considers the following as criteria for recognizing current (current) assets:

“1. It is part of the operating activities of an economic entity and is expected to be acquired and consumed within the normal operating cycle of the entity.

2. It is held primarily for the purpose of resale or is expected to be used in the short term or within 12 months from the reporting date.”

Analyzing this situation, it is appropriate to use the term company or organization instead of the term “economic entity”. It is also incorrect to consider current assets as part of operating activities, they participate in operating activities. It is advisable to change these aspects.

In accordance with IAS 21, the chart of accounts [4] includes the following sections for accounting for current assets: “1. Goods and tangible assets, 2. Deferred and deferred expenses - current portion, 3. Accounts receivable, 4. Cash, short-term investments and other current assets.”

This structure also needs to be brought into line with international standards. For example, “goods and tangible assets” is a general economic concept, and the concepts used in accounting should be clear and concise. Therefore, it would be appropriate to call it “reserves”

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, abstract-logical thinking, monographic observation, methods of economic analysis and mathematical formulas were used in the research work. With the help of these methods, the scientific literature on the subject was critically studied, the current regulatory and legal documents were studied from the point of view of improvement, and the financial reporting forms in the practice of enterprises were analyzed from the point of view of content and form.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the accounting sense, economic resources are a set of non-current and current assets (resources) attracted to an organization in order to generate profit.

Non-current assets include natural resources (subsoil resources), real estate (land, buildings and structures), investment properties, machinery and equipment, intangible assets, biological assets, long-term investments.

Current assets or current assets are assets that circulate during the operating cycle of an organization and transfer their value to newly created products. They include inventories, accounts receivable, public funds and other current assets.

Requirements for economic resources characterize the ownership rights and obligations to economic resources. These include equity and liabilities.

According to international standards, economic resources and requirements change due to two factors:

1. Financial results
2. Other factors not related to financial results

Information on the financial results of a reporting enterprise helps users describe the extent to which the organization has benefited from the economic resources available to it. This information is useful in assessing the extent to which the organization’s management has fulfilled its obligations regarding the rational use of resources. Financial results are the main source of increasing resources. Financial results assess the organization’s ability to generate net cash from economic resources. If the company ends the reporting year with a loss, these events lead to a decrease in economic resources

Economic resources can also change due to factors not related to financial results. Examples of these factors include the issuance of shares to increase participation in additional capital or the introduction of additional capital by the founders. Information about these changes is necessary for users to understand the factors that have caused the reporting entity’s economic resources and demands on them.

Current assets make a significant contribution to the economic resources of the enterprise, regularly circulate in the operating cycle, and transfer their value to newly created products.

In the conceptual framework, the following are noted as elements of financial reporting (picture 1)

Picture 1. Elements of financial reporting

The new conceptual framework, effective from 2018, defines assets as follows:
Assets are current economic resources that are controlled by the company as a result of past events.

An economic resource is a right that has the potential to generate economic benefits.

Although absolute certainty is not required for economic benefits to be generated, it is required that the right be exercised and, in specific circumstances, generate economic benefits for the company that exceed those that could be obtained by all other parties.

It has been established that rights, potential for creating economic benefits and control of assets.

IAS No. 1 "Presentation of Financial Statements" standard specifies the content of information on assets. We describe their naming as follows (table-1)

Components of assets in accordance with IAS "Presentation of Financial Statements" standard No. 1

Types of assets (in Uzbek)	Types of assets (in Russian)	Types of assets (in English)	Non-current or current assets
Real estate, plant and machinery and equipment	Основные средства	Property, plant and equipment	Non-current asset
Investment property	Инвестиционная собственность	Investment property	Non-current asset
Intangible assets	Нематериальные активы	Intangible assets	Non-current asset
Financial assets	Финансовые активы	Financial assets	Current assets
Investments accounted for by the equity method	Инвестиции, учитываемые по методу долевого участия	Investments accounted for using the equity method	Non-current asset
Biological assets	Биологические активы	Biological assets	Non-current asset
Reserves	Запасы	Inventories	Current assets
Trade and other receivables	Торговая и прочая дебиторская задолженность	Trade and other receivables	Current assets
Cash and cash equivalents	Денежные средства и их эквиваленты	Cash and cash equivalents	Current assets
Non-current assets held for sale and assets of exiting groups held for sale	Внеоборотные активы, предназначенные для продажи, и активы выбывающей группы, предназначенной для продажи	Assets classified as held for sale, and assets indicated in disposal groups classified as held for sale	Current assets
Current and deferred tax assets (separate)	Текущие и отложенные налоговые активы (отдельно)	Current and deferred tax assets (separately)	Non-current and current assets

Based on this table, we can divide assets into two groups depending on their participation in turnover:

1. Non-current assets (their composition is given in the table);
2. Current (current) assets (their composition is given in the table).

According to the requirements of the standard, in order to be recognized as current (current) assets, it is noted that it must meet the following requirements (table-2)

Criteria for recognizing current assets and their content

Naming criteria	Content
1. It is intended to be sold or held for sale or used in the company’s normal operating cycle	Intended for sale means that the asset is sold; held for sale means that the reserve is held for sale; used in the operating cycle means that raw materials are held as reserves for production
2. It is intended to be held for trading	Intended for trading means that the asset is purchased with the intention of reselling
3. It is intended to be sold within 12 months after the reporting date	Any asset that is expected to be sold within 12 months after the reporting date, that is, intended for sale, is considered a current asset. Trade and other receivables are also considered current assets if they are expected to be settled within 12 months.
4. Assets in the form of cash and cash equivalents	The most liquid asset that has no obstacles to use and can be quickly converted into other assets

These criteria serve as the basis for recognizing current assets. Recognized and valued current assets are reflected in the statements at their balance sheet value.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, the work revealed the essence of the concept of economic resources and requirements. It was emphasized that their composition should be developed in accordance with international standards. A definition of assets and current assets in the sense of accounting was developed. We believe that it is necessary to rework the description and composition of current assets in our current regulatory legal documents.

The work developed a composition of assets, including current assets, that meets the requirements of international standards. Conceptual foundations, proposals for improving the standards of IAS 1 “Accounting Policies and Financial Reporting” were presented. In practice, the reflection of current assets in the balance sheet by composition was studied and directions for their improvement were identified. In particular, proposals were made to reduce lines, combine inventories into one item, and classify receivables into trade and non-trade types.

The implementation of these proposals and recommendations will serve to bring the accounting and reporting of current assets into line with international standards, and to increase the quality of the information reflected in the reports.

REFERENCES:

1. *Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2020 No. PQ-4611 "On additional measures for the transition to international financial reporting standards"*. <https://lex.uz/docs/4746047>
2. "Conceptual foundations of financial reporting" https://www.minfin.ru/common/upload/library/2014/06/main/kontseptualnye_osnovy_na_sayt_bez_predisloviya_-_kopiya.pdf
3. NSA No. 1 "Accounting policies and financial reporting". <https://lex.uz/nsbu>
4. NSA No. 21 "The plan of accounting accounts for the financial and economic activities of economic entities and instructions for its application" <https://lex.uz/acts/809350>
5. *Accounting in English (pp.51) Publisher: Printed by: Dar Al-Dhiya for printing and Designs - 2 Ed, - Najaf - February 2019* https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331287344_CHAPTER_4_CURRENT_ASSETS
6. <https://byjus.com/commerce/what-are-current-assets/>
7. Hosted by Neil Amato. *Digital assets: Auditing, accounting, and what's next* December 3, 2021 <https://www.journalofaccountancy.com/podcast/cpa-news-digital-assets-auditing-accounting.html>
8. Karimov A.A., Kurbanbayev J.E., Jumanazarov S.A. *Accounting. Textbook // -T.: "Economics-Finance", 2019. 624 p.*
9. Tuychiyev A.J. and others, *Audit. Textbook. - T.: "Economics-Finance", 2019.- 416 p.*
10. Nurmanov U.A. *Improving the accounting and analysis of current assets. // Abstract of the dissertation submitted for the degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences. T.: 2012. 26 p.*
11. Mavlyanova D.M. *Improving the methodological aspects of accounting, analysis and audit of current assets. // Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics. T.: 2020.*